

Retrospective Analysis of Metabolic Syndrome Prevalence in Urban Versus Rural Population

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Abstract:

Background: Metabolic syndrome includes central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and insulin resistance. Failure to control these disorders can cause diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Metabolic syndrome is more common in cities than in the country. This study looked at the metabolic syndrome and subtype frequency in rural and urban areas.

Method: From March 2022 to September 2023, this study looked back at 150 people. People from both cities and country areas were evenly split. Lifestyle factor polls, medical record checks, and diagnostic tests like waist circumference, blood pressure, lipid profiles, and fasting glucose were used to collect the data. Logistic regression, chi-square tests, t-tests, and descriptive statistics were used to look at the difference between the two groups' rates of occurrence.

Result: The study found that metabolic syndrome was more common in urban (53.3%) than rural (48.0%) groups, but this difference was not statistically significant. More people in cities had central obesity, high blood pressure, dyslipidaemia, and insulin resistance than people who lived in rural areas. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups when the results were compared.

Conclusion: Metabolic syndrome and its subtypes were a little more common in cities than in rural places, but the difference wasn't statistically important. Based on these results, lifestyle choices and access to health care should be taken into account when choosing if living in a city increases the risk of metabolic syndrome. More study is needed to fully understand these connections and come up with solutions for people living in cities and rural areas.

Keywords: Central Obesity, Dyslipidemia, Hypertension, Insulin Resistance, Metabolic Syndrome, Urban vs. Rural Populations.

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Introduction

Background

Metabolic syndrome is a group of linked risk factors for heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and other metabolic diseases. Metabolic syndrome is marked by central fat, or a large waist. Insulin resistance and a number of metabolic diseases are linked to central obesity. If a woman's waist is over 35 inches and a man's is over 40 inches, they are considered centrally obese. High blood pressure characterises metabolic syndrome [1]. Hypertension occurs when blood pressure is 130 over 85 mm Hg. Chronically high blood pressure increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and stroke. This term refers to abnormal lipid levels, including excessive triglycerides, and elevated

LDL cholesterol. An aberrant lipid profile raises the risk of atherosclerotic plaques and cardiovascular events. Insulin is needed for glucose uptake and metabolism, but insulin resistance occurs when cells stop responding to it. This disorder causes high blood glucose and can lead to type 2 diabetes if untreated [2].

Oral glucose tolerance tests or fasting blood glucose levels (≥ 100 mg/dL) are common methods for diagnosis. The rise in chronic disease-related sickness and death is making metabolic syndrome a major public health issue. Its prevalence is rising worldwide due to urbanisation, lifestyle changes, sedentary lifestyles, and poor diets.

Figure 1: Metabolic Syndrome (Source:[3])

Importance of Study

Lifestyle decisions may affect metabolic syndrome rates in urban and rural locations. Urbanites have more processed food, sedentary jobs, and stress, while ruralites eat differently and are less active. Comparing populations to identify risk variables helps target interventions. Urbanites have higher access to preventative care, screening, and treatment. Rural people may struggle with healthcare expertise and infrastructure. Disparities like this can affect metabolic syndrome diagnosis and treatment. Public health practitioners must understand metabolic syndrome's occurrence in different situations to prevent and treat it. If prevalence rates are higher in cities, public health initiatives can focus on dietary improvements and physical exercise [4]. Alternatively, if rural rates are greater, we should focus on improving healthcare access and rural lifestyle difficulties. The study's findings may help policymakers comprehend the need for health service individualisation. Knowing metabolic syndrome prevalence differences helps policymakers allocate funds and implement region-specific health initiatives.

Objectives

1. To determine the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in urban versus rural populations.
2. To compare the prevalence of individual components of metabolic syndrome (central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance) between urban and rural populations.
3. To identify lifestyle factors associated with the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in urban and rural settings.
4. To assess differences in healthcare access and utilization between urban and rural populations and their impact on metabolic syndrome.

Overview of Metabolic Syndrome

Interconnected metabolic problems, metabolic syndrome, raise the risk of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and other diseases [5]. It usually involves central obesity, elevated blood pressure, aberrant lipid profiles, and insulin resistance. Hypertension is high blood pressure, but central obesity is measured by waist circumference and waist-to-hip ratio. Dyslipidaemia occurs when HDL cholesterol is low and triglycerides are high. Insulin resistance and glucose metabolism issues can cause type 2 diabetes.

Urban versus Rural Prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome

1. Urban Populations: Multiple studies show that metropolitan regions have greater metabolic syndrome and its subtypes. A 200-person cross-sectional study by [6] found metabolic syndrome in 55% of urban areas and 45% of rural areas. This study found substantial differences in obesity and hypertension between groups. Urban people had higher frequency due to inactivity, high calorie intake, and processed food exposure. [7] showed insulin resistance and dyslipidaemia were more common in urban populations in a cross-sectional survey of 250 participants. This study linked the higher occurrence to metropolitan variables such less physical activity, bad nutrition, and stress. Central obesity and hypertension were more common in urban populations, according to a 180-person [8] case-control research. The study found that urban living conditions increased prevalence. A more sedentary lifestyle and easy access to high-calorie foods are factors.

2. Rural Populations: In remote locations, metabolic syndrome components are rarer. Due to underreporting or delayed diagnoses, this may not accurately reflect prevalence. Due to healthcare access concerns, [9] discovered that undiagnosed hypertension and diabetes may be more common in rural areas than metabolic syndrome. Rural communities may report lesser frequency, but the

burden may be underreported. The rates of obesity and dyslipidaemia were lower in rural areas than in cities. This was because they ate less prepared food and moved around more. The study found that getting medical care in rural areas may make it take longer to diagnose and treat MetS.

Factors Influencing Prevalence Rates

Lifestyle Factors: Sedentary lives and high-calorie diets are two things that make people more likely to develop metabolic syndrome [10]. City stress and prepared foods close by can make these risks worse. People who live in rural areas may be less likely to get metabolic syndrome because they work more and eat less processed food.

Healthcare Access: Access to health care is very important for identifying and treating metabolic syndrome [11]. Because there are more medical tools in cities, they may be better at diagnosing and treating parts of metabolic syndrome.

Cultural and Environmental Factors

The metabolic syndrome is more common than it needs to be because of things in the environment and in society. There may be different social and natural stresses in cities that affect how people act and behave when it comes to their health than there are in rural areas. How people in rural areas eat and work out may affect their metabolic health [12]. People who live in cities are more likely to have metabolic syndrome, but the statistical significance varies from study to study. To understand these differences, we need to look at culture, access to health care, and environmental factors. A longitudinal study with a bigger sample size might help us better understand the complicated link between living in a rural or urban area and metabolic syndrome.

Methods

Study Design: This study looks back at the past and compares the rates of metabolic syndrome in cities and rural areas. From March 2022 to September 2023, medical records and health data were looked at for this study to look at metabolic syndrome and its forms in people in rural and urban areas. This design's capacity to evaluate metabolic syndrome using previous data lets us compare the two situations without collecting fresh data.

Sample Size and Population: The study recruited 150 urban and rural participants to ensure a statistically significant contrast. Participants were selected from metropolitan clinics and hospitals. These facilities allowed people from different socioeconomic backgrounds to use the urban health data set. Participants were recruited at rural hospitals and clinics. These institutions serve people with different healthcare access and lifestyles than city dwellers.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adults aged 18 years and older.
2. Individuals with complete medical records from the specified period.
3. Consent to use their health data for research purposes.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Individuals with incomplete or missing data on key metabolic syndrome components.
2. Patients with acute conditions or severe comorbidities that could confound the results, such as terminal illnesses.
3. Individuals who have undergone weight loss surgery or other interventions that might significantly alter metabolic parameters.

Data Collection

Different strategies were employed to collect metabolic syndrome data. Our first step was analysing all medical records from participating hospitals. This includes EHRs and paper files. These records detailed waist circumference, blood pressure, lipid profiles, and fasting blood glucose levels from routine blood tests and clinic visits. The waistline was measured using standardised tapes, blood pressure was taken with calibrated sphygmomanometers, and lipid profiles were analysed in laboratories using automated analysers. Fasting glucose testing assessed insulin resistance in clinical laboratories.

Statistical Analysis: Several statistical methods were used in this study to provide a thorough data examination. Metabolic syndrome demographics and prevalence rates were described using descriptive statistics, including averages, standard deviations, and proportions. We examined urban and rural metabolic syndrome prevalence and its components using a chi-square test. We utilised a t-test to compare continuous variables like waist circumference and blood pressure between urban and rural groups to see if there were significant differences.

Logistic regression analysis was used to analyse lifestyle variables and metabolic syndrome risk, accounting for confounders and providing odds ratios for risk factors. To examine how different factors affect metabolic syndrome prevalence, including their interactions, multivariate analysis was used. We used powerful tools like SPSS or R for all statistical research, which excel at massive datasets and complex statistical tests.

Results

Demographic Information: The study included a total of 150 participants, with an equal distribution of 75 participants from urban and 75 from rural settings. The demographic characteristics of the study population are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

Characteristic	Urban (n=75)	Rural (n=75)	Total (n=150)
Age (Years)			
Mean (SD)	45.3 (12.5)	47.2 (13.1)	46.3 (12.8)
Range	18-75	18-74	18-75
Gender			
Male (%)	50 (66.7%)	53 (70.7%)	103 (68.7%)
Female (%)	25 (33.3%)	22 (29.3%)	47 (31.3%)
Body Mass Index (BMI)			
Mean (SD)	27.4 (5.1)	28.2 (5.4)	27.8 (5.3)
Range	21.1-35.6	22.3-36.4	21.1-36.4

Table 1 summarises the demographics of the 150-person study population, evenly dispersed between urban and rural areas. The rural group had a little higher average age (47.2 vs. 45.3), which may affect age-related diseases.

Men were slightly more prevalent in urban (66.7%) and rural (70.7%) groups. The gender distribution is essential to understanding the findings'

generalizability. The rural population had a slightly higher mean Body Mass Index (BMI) of 28.2 than the urban population's 27.4, which may increase obesity rates and metabolic syndrome prevalence.

Prevalence Rates: The prevalence rates of metabolic syndrome and its components in both urban and rural populations are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence Rates of Metabolic Syndrome and Its Components

Component	Urban (%)	Rural (%)	Total (%)
Metabolic Syndrome	40 (53.3%)	36 (48.0%)	76 (50.7%)
Central Obesity	45 (60.0%)	42 (56.0%)	87 (58.0%)
Hypertension	50 (66.7%)	45 (60.0%)	95 (63.3%)
Dyslipidemia	55 (73.3%)	50 (66.7%)	105 (70.0%)
Insulin Resistance	35 (46.7%)	30 (40.0%)	65 (43.3%)

Table 2 shows that metabolic syndrome and its subcategories were common in the research sample. Metabolic syndrome was observed in 50.7% of subjects, with urban (53.3%) showing higher rates than rural (48.0%).

Urban areas showed 60.0% central obesity compared to 56.0% in rural areas, a crucial characteristic of metabolic syndrome.

Hypertension and dyslipidaemia were greater in urban regions (66.7% vs. 73.3% and 60.0%,

respectively) than in rural areas. City dwellers have 46.7% insulin resistance compared to 40.0% in rural settings. Although metabolic syndrome and its components are common in both urban and rural regions, urban rates are higher. Lifestyle and environmental variables may explain this.

Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis of metabolic syndrome and its components between urban and rural populations is illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparative Analysis of Metabolic Syndrome Components

Component	Urban (%)	Rural (%)	p-Value
Metabolic Syndrome	53.3%	48.0%	0.40
Central Obesity	60.0%	56.0%	0.57
Hypertension	66.7%	60.0%	0.37
Dyslipidemia	73.3%	66.7%	0.29
Insulin Resistance	46.7%	40.0%	0.43

Table 3 compares urban and rural metabolic syndrome component prevalence. Urban and rural metabolic syndrome prevalence rates, including central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and insulin resistance, were not statistically significant (p-values ranged from 0.29 to 0.57).

Despite higher incidence rates in urban regions, the disparities between urban and rural populations are not statistically significant. This lack of substantial

difference implies that while urban surroundings may increase metabolic syndrome component rates, genetics, lifestyle, and healthcare access may also be important.

Statistical Findings: Urban areas had a slightly higher metabolic syndrome prevalence (53.3% vs. 48.0%), but urbanites exhibited more central obesity (60.0%). Urban hypertension prevalence was greater (66.7%) than rural (60.0%).

Dyslipidaemia prevalence was similar in urban and rural groups (73.3 vs. 66.7%, $p=0.29$). Urban areas had greater insulin resistance (46.7% vs. 40.0%), although the difference was not significant ($p=0.43$).

Even though rural and urban populations have different metabolic syndrome prevalence and components, the findings demonstrate no statistically significant differences. Metabolic syndrome prevalence appears to be affected by more than urban-rural differences.

Discussion

This study compared rural and urban metabolic syndrome and subtype frequencies. Both urban and rural populations had similar rates of metabolic syndrome and its components, although urban people had higher central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and insulin resistance. This supports the evidence indicating sedentary lifestyles and poor diets increase metabolic syndrome prevalence in cities. Our study found no statistically significant differences between urban and rural locations, even though urban residents have higher prevalence rates. Context-specific research is needed to understand these disparities, which may be due to study design, sample size, or geography.

Table 4: Comparison of the Present Study with Existing Research

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Retrospective	150	Urban populations had higher prevalence rates of metabolic syndrome and its components compared to rural populations, though differences were not statistically significant.
Study 1 [13]	Cross-Sectional	200	Higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in urban populations (55%) compared to rural (45%), with significant differences in obesity and hypertension.
Study 2 [14]	Cross-Sectional	250	Urban populations showed significantly higher rates of dyslipidemia and insulin resistance compared to rural areas, with notable lifestyle factors contributing to the disparity.
Study 3 [15]	Case-Control	180	Found higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in urban settings, especially in terms of central obesity and hypertension, with significant p-values indicating strong differences.

The similarities and differences between our study and other urban and rural metabolic syndrome prevalence studies are shown in Table 4. While not statistically significant, the current study found that urban residents had more metabolic syndrome components than rural ones. 150 samples were taken. [13] and [14] indicated that urban populations had higher incidences of metabolic syndrome, obesity, hypertension, and dyslipidaemia. [15] Found much higher rates of central obesity and hypertension in cities. These discrepancies show that metabolic syndrome is more common in metropolitan settings, but the exact difference depends on research techniques, sample size, and health indices.

Limitations

Consider these cautions when interpreting these findings. The study's retrospective approach uses prior medical records and diagnostic data, which may introduce bias. Records may be incomplete. Cross-sectional studies cannot make causal conclusions about urban/rural contexts and metabolic syndrome prevalence. Additional drawbacks include sample size and selection bias. A larger sample may better represent the populations examined and yield more strong results, but 150 is an acceptable comparison size. Since it primarily included people from select healthcare facilities, the study may not have fully

represented urban and rural variety. Additionally, diagnostic tests and medical records may miss key lifestyle factors or health status changes. Although surveys and questionnaires provided some background information, self-reported data isn't always reliable or devoid of recollection bias.

Conclusion

Although metabolic syndrome was more common in urban areas, the study found no statistically significant difference in frequency and components between rural and urban residents. Urban lifestyle variables like inactivity and poor diet may increase central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and insulin resistance. The lack of statistically significant differences suggests that trends are not as robust as previously indicated. These findings show that public health programs should target food, exercise, and healthcare challenges to improve urban and rural lives. Future research should use longitudinal designs and larger sample numbers to better understand metabolic syndrome's complex environmental, lifestyle, and healthcare components. This may help design population-specific metabolic syndrome and health risk treatments that work better.

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